

Integrating Artificial Intelligence into Social Studies Education: A Strategy for Fostering Innovative Pedagogy and Sustainability in the 21st Century

Lawal Halilu, PhD

Department of Social Studies

Federal University of Education, Zaria

Kaduna State, Nigeria

08036083242, lawalhalilu492@gmail.com

This paper examines the potential of integrating artificial intelligence (AI) into Social Studies Education as a strategy for fostering innovative pedagogies in teaching and learning, especially in an era defined by rapid technological advancement and complex global challenges. Equipping young learners with innovation in the classroom has become imperative. The paper provides conceptual frameworks of artificial intelligence, the curriculum of modern Social Studies Education, quest for innovation and sustainability. The paper discussed the relevance of artificial intelligence (AI) applications in Social Studies, reviewed some studies of artificial intelligence in social studies classroom settings, and evaluated the benefits and challenges of using artificial intelligence as a modern tool for teaching and learning in the subject. The paper concludes by proposing a strategic framework for the sustainable integration of AI in Social Studies Education for future curriculum designers. Recommendations were made for policymakers, educators and technology developers on the relevance of integrating artificial intelligence (AI) into Social Studies in the 21st century.

Keywords:
Artificial Intelligence, Social Studies Education, Innovative pedagogies Sustainability.

Introduction

In an era marked by rapid technological advancement and intensifying global challenges, it is Imperative to embrace an innovative pedagogy-driven mindset in social studies classroom operation. Technological forces, particularly artificial intelligence (AI), are fundamentally reshaping the structures of economics, societies and the education system. These shifts present both profound opportunities and pressing responsibilities for those tasked with preparing the next generation for an interconnected world (UNESCO, 2023; Schwab, 2016). Artificial intelligence (AI) transformed a broad spectrum of sectors, from healthcare and public policy to

psychological and environmental science (Su et -al, 2023; Xu et -al, 2021). In education, AI technologies are harnessed to personalise instruction, automate assessment, predict learner performance and recommend adaptive learning pathways (Yahaya and Mohammed, 2024). However, significant scholarly attention has been paid to the implications of AI. Social Studies education, a substantial gap in understanding its role and potential within the stages of teaching and learning.

The integration of artificial intelligent into social studies education is not merely a question of technological enhancement; it is a strategic consideration in nurturing future

citizens who are both innovative and environmentally responsible. Integrating artificial intelligence in social studies instruction is a innovative pedagogical practices through intelligent, interactive and inclusive learning environments, these which can foster critical 21st century competencies such as creativity, problem solving, empathy and ecological awareness especially when deployed within culturally relevant and ethically sound framework (Luakin et-al, Zulb; Chen et al, 2021).

Furthermore, the integration of AI into Social Studies Education aligns with global policy priorities, such as the United Nation Sustainable Development Goal 4.2 which calls for equitable access to quality education particularly in resource - constrained setting; AI has the potential to address disparities in access and quality by offering scalable, data- driven solutions.

However, barriers to effective teaching, and learning in Social Studies are compounded by the lack of resources and digital tools to students' diverse learning styles. Traditional teaching approach have been slow to adapt active learning strategies and often do not address the differences among learners, particularly those tied to language and engagement levels. This static instructional approach limits students' ability to fully comprehend Social Studies teaching, making it challenging for them to retain content and ultimately reducing their academic performance. In view of the foregoing reflections, this study, therefore, seeks to fill gap by exploring how AI integration can enhance teaching, and learning of Social Studies.

Integrating Artificial Intelligence into Social Studies Education

The integration of artificial intelligence in Social Studies Education has

already begun to revolutionize traditional methods and broaden the scope of personalized learning experiences. AI applications in Social Studies education range from automated grading systems and real -time analytics to tools for managing learning progress, providing individual feed- back, and creating interactive learning environment (Zawacki Richter et al, 2019). In particular, AI- powered tools used in Social Studies Classrooms can offer immediate and accurate feedback on assignments provide formative assessments and identify areas where students may need additional support, thus streamlining the overall learning experience (Holmes, Bialik and Fadel, 2019). One of AI's transformative contributions to Social Studies education is its ability to make learning more accessible to students with disabilities. Advancements in Natural Language Processing and Computer Vision. AI has facilitated the creation of tools that generate lecture transcripts, provide reel -time language, translation, and adapt learning material to meet diverse accessibility needs (Chan, et al, 2020). Moreover, AI-driven educational platforms that incorporate ramifications, simulations and virtual environments encourage interactive and experimental learning, which can be particularly valuable for subjects requiring practical application or visualization, such as Social Studies education (Anderson and Makori, 2021). The relevance of Artificial intelligence in Social Studies education was highlighted further during Covid-19 pandemic, as schools turned to digital learning platforms. The demand for AI-powered educational tools surged, emphasizing the need for resilient, adaptable educational technologies capable of operating across varied learning environments and addressing the limitations of traditional educational models (Xie, Sigu and Wah, 2020).

Akavova, A. Temirkhanova, Z. (2023), conducted a study Titled “Adoptive

Learning and Integrating of Artificial Intelligence into Social Studies Education”. To explore the integration adoptive learning technologies with artificial intelligence to enhance personalized learning experiences. The study followed a mixed- methods design involving a population of 500 students across various educational institutions, selected through purposive sampling to represent diverse learning needs. The instruments used include AI-Powered learning platforms that collected and analyzed vast amount of performance data, providing personalized feedback and recommendations. Data were analyzed using statistical tools such as descriptive statistics and regression analysis to evaluate the impact of personalized interventions. The findings revealed that AI- Powered adaptive learning systems significantly improved learning outcomes in Social Studies Education by identifying areas of weakness and providing targeted interventions, which in turn increased student engagement and motivation. Additionally, these systems helped teachers by automating administrative tasks and offering real-time feedback. The authors concluded that while AI and adoptive learning hold great potential in revolutionizing Social Studies Instruction, challenges such as privacy concerns, ethical issues, and the need for teacher training must be addressed. They recommended further research into overcoming these challenges to maximize the benefit of these technologies in Social Studies Education.

The Curriculum of Modern Social Studies Education

Professional Social Studies teacher needs to accept and propagate the view that we are operating in an era defined by rapid

technological advancement and complex global challenges, equipping learners with innovative pedagogies such as AI into classroom delivery has become necessary. The Social Studies curriculum content must be seen as an artifact, which is to be contrived as a basis for solving the problems created by separate subject approach in the curriculum of schools. This curriculum package is expected to provide young learners with some insight into the use of various knowledge structures and processes that have bearing on modern civilization. Since Social Studies is intended to offer a curriculum that is both relevant and meaningful to young learners that demand personal and social understanding, Social Studies may be concerned with the production and propagation of knowledge for its own sake as with the utilization of knowledge derived from a variety of disciplines, including the Social Sciences, for the purpose of solving problems through various processes.

The Quest for Integrating Innovative pedagogies into Social Studies Education

Innovation encompasses the ability to conceive and implement novel, ideas, methods, or solutions that offer improvements or address emerging challenges. Innovation is cultivated in an increasing dynamic and unpredictable global environment. Thinking about teaching and learning is essential. It encourages children to explore, experiment, adapt and apply knowledge creatively across contexts from science and technology to arts and entrepreneurship.

Tidd and Bessant; (2022); describe innovation as a multidimensional process in which knowledge, with Social Studies education fostering innovation provides students with skills competencies, moral

values and reasoned judgments to effectively live, interact, interrelate and contribute positively to the economic, social and political development of Nigerian society that is essential for thriving in the 21st century knowledge economy (Okam, 2019).

Exploring Sustainable Pedagogies into Social Studies Education

Sustainability is broadly defined as meeting the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs. This encompasses environmental stewardship, social equity, and economic resilience. In Social Studies Education, sustainability translates into pedagogies that nurture ecological awareness, ethical reasoning and global citizenship. Introducing sustainability concept during Social Studies instruction fosters lifelong attitudes and behaviors that align with responsible living and systematic thinking. When integrated with AI meaningful learning was enhanced. Sustainability can be personalized and made more engaging thereby reinforcing value of conservation inclusion; and interdependence.

Relevance of Integrating Artificial Intelligence (AI) in Social Studies Education as a Innovative Pedagogy in Teaching and Learning

Artificial intelligence (AI) is becoming an increasingly transformative force across sections including education. In the realm of Social Studies Education, the relevance of AI technologies in teaching and learning offers exciting opportunities to enhance cognitive, affective and psychomotor development; foster creativity; and support inclusive learning. However, these advancements remain largely

underutilized in many African contexts including Nigeria (Ogunode and Edokhamher, 2024).

Artificial intelligence refers to the strategic use of intelligent techniques such as machine learning, natural language processing and data driven tools to create responsive, adoptive, and child-friendly learning experiences. These tools are designed not to replace educators caregivers but to complement their effort, optimize instruction and personalize learning pathways for young learners during their critical developmental years (UNESCO, 2023). The Relevance of Integrating Artificial Intelligence into Social Studies Education for the professional teacher of the subject as reflected thus,

- i. Fostering Innovation from the Early Age of the Learners:** Artificial intelligence tools such as smart tablets for phonics or interactive storybooks such as Kibo can provide meaningful learning, and engage learning experiences that help and solve problems independently (UNESCO, 2023). This early exposure to adaptive learning not only boosts individual development but also sets the stage for a generation capable of driving technological innovation in teaching, learning, and sustainability in the 21st century. (Fitas, 2023).
- ii. Promoting Inclusive and Equated Education:** In a culturally and linguistically diverse country like Nigeria, AI can play a vital role in ensuring equity in AI-driven translation, speech, recognition and special needs learning tools can help children with disabilities or from minority language groups access quality (Fitas, 2025; UNESCO, 2023). This aligns with the

nation's commitment to inclusive education as part of the Sustainable Development Goal (SDGS).

- iii. **Enhancing teacher Effectiveness and Development:** AI can support Social Studies professionals by automating repetitive tasks such as attendance and grading and offering insights into students, learning patterns (The Cable, 2024). This allows teachers to focus more on pedagogy and relationship building with learners. Moreover, AI-powered platforms can offer on-demand professional development a much-needed tool in regions where access to training is limited (The Guardian Nigeria, 2023).
- iv. **Driving Responsible Innovation in Social Studies Instruction:** Innovation is at the heart of integrating AI into Social Studies instruction. AI tools can support phonics learning, personalize story teaching, or even help learners with special needs, interact more fully into the classroom environment (UNESCO, 2023). However, innovation must be purposefully tailored to the developmental needs of young learners and aligned with the local educational goals.
- v. **The Role of Policy Scaling and Safeguarding AI Integration in Social Studies Education:** Policy is the backbone of Social Studies education that supports and regulates innovation and ethics. A clear national AI in Social Studies education policy keeps guiding standards, accountability, data government, funding, and equitable access. Without such a framework, AI tools may be deployed in frame ways, lending to inequality or misuse.

In Nigeria, calls have been made by experts and educators to incorporate AI into national educators strategies and curricular, ensuring that AI is not just adopted, but aligned with national development priorities (The Guadiana Nigeria, 2023) Policy also enables collaboration between government, private technical companies, and civil society, ensuring that no one stakeholders dominates or distorts the purpose of integrating AI into Social Studies Education.

Strategy for Fostering Innovative pedagogies and Application of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in Social Studies Education

Integrating artificial intelligence as innovative pedagogy in Social Studies Curriculum design will reshape learners mindset by enabling personalized, engaging, and developmentally appropriate learning experiences when implemented effectively, which can enhance school readiness, boost cognitive outcomes, and reduce educational inequalities. Some innovative applications of artificial intelligence (AI) in Social Studies Education in various schools settings are as follows:

- i. **Personalized learning Application:** Applications of AI such as Lingokids, Osmo, and Khan Academy Kids, utilize machine learning to tailor content to each child's needs by adjusting in real time to promote mastery of early literacy, numeracy and problem-solving skills (Richter et-al, 2023).
- ii. **Smart Toys and Robots:** Interactive robots such as Miko and Cozmo use Social recognition and voice interactions to support inquiry-based learning. These tools encourage curiosity and active engagement, aligning with modern Social Studies objectives (Chen, et al, 2023).

- iii. **Early Diagnosis and Inclusion:** AI tools leveraging speech recognition and computer vision can identify developmental delay's or learning difficulties early, thus allowing for interventions (UNICEF, 2023).
- iv. **AI Assisted teacher Support:** AI can assist a professional teacher of Social Studies by automating lesson planning and assessments, freeing up time for emotional and social engagement with students (UNESCO, 2023).
- v. **Conceptual relevance in Nigeria:** In Nigeria, AI can address disparities in access by delivering content via solar-powered – devices in local languages, and local edtech developers and is well positioned to design culturally appropriate solutions that resonate with Nigerian learners (Adebayo and Salisu, 2023).

Framework of Sustainable Integration of Artificial Intelligence into Social Studies Education in the 21st Century

Artificial intelligence integration in Social Studies education supports sustainability across environmental, economic, social and institutional settings;

- i. **Environmental Sustainability:** AI-based platforms reduce reliance on printed materials, lowering educational waste, when powered by renewable energy sources such as solar panels, which are especially viable for off-grid Nigerian communities (World Bank, 2022).
- ii. **Economic Sustainability:** Although initial costs are high, AI becomes cost- effective overtime through scalable content automated systems and decreased reliance on physical resources (Adebayo and Salisu, 2023).
- iii. **Social Sustainability:** AI supports inclusive education through personalized learning, multilingual resources, and access to marginalized groups which help bridge gaps

across socio-economic and geographic divides (Okonkwo and Adeyemi, 2023).

- iv. **Institutional and Professional Sustainability:** AI provides educators with real-time data on child development and support informed teaching. Additionally, AI-driven training platforms can enhance professional development and build a resilient and adaptive workforce (UNESCO, 2023).

Challenges of Integrating Artificial Intelligence in Social Studies Education in Nigeria

Nigeria faces several; challenges in integrating artificial intelligence in Social Studies curriculum as follows:

- i. **Infrastructural Deficiencies:** Many Social Studies workshops lack electricity; internet access and digital devices especially in rural areas (Lawal and Njokwu, 2025).
- ii. **Limited teacher Preparedness:** Low digital literacy and limited training among Social Studies teachers hinders effective AI adoption in schools and colleges. (Okonkwo and Adeyemi, 2023).
- iii. **Financial Constraints:** AI tools are expensive and many schools cannot afford hardware, software and maintenance without external support (Adebayo and Salisu, 2023).
- iv. **Cultural resistance and Trust Concerns:** Skepticism about screen time, machine interaction, and data privacy slows AI acceptance among Social Studies teachers. (Eke, 2022).

Conclusion

The main argument for the emergence of Artificial intelligence into Social Studies Education of the Modern Curricular represent reaction against the traditional approaches in Social Studies

instruction. AI-driven makes learning more inclusive, adaptive, and engaging. The paper examines the concept of Artificial Intelligence, how the curriculum of modern Social Studies differ from the tradition curriculum, demonstrate application of AI into Social Studies instruction, strategies for fostering innovative pedagogies were outlined. Framework of sustainable integration of Artificial Intelligence highlighted, challenges and recommendations were provided.

Recommendations

If artificial intelligence is to be employed in teaching of Social Studies education in our institution of learning as a innovative instructional paradigm tool for attaining the objectives in the curriculum design of the subject, the following recommendations are made:

- i. **Create a National framework for AI in education:** The Federal Ministry of Education, in partnership with technology experts and educators, should develop a national policy on AI in Social Studies teaching and learning. This framework should include clear guidelines for ethical AI use, data profession measures, strategies for curriculum integration, and path- ways for equitable access, particularly in Social Studies classroom dispensation.
- ii. **Strengthen Digital Infrastructure:** Improving access to digital infrastructure is critical especially in rural and underserved communities. This involves ensuring reliable electricity, affordable Internet, and child-friendly smart devices. Leveraging solar power and offline AI solutions can help bridge the digital divide and support a sustainable learning environment (ITU, 2024).

- iii. **Equip teachers with AI Skills:** Teachers are key to successful AI adoption in Social Studies, and regular training programmes should be introduced to help them understand how to appropriately use AI tools. In addition, teacher education institutions should update their curricular to include modules of AI, digital pedagogy, and data ethics.
- iv. **Increase Public Awareness:** Public campaigns should aim to educate parents on what AI is, how it supports learning and hours to balance its use with social interaction and play. Community engagement is essential to building trust and ensuring that AI tools are meaningfully used at home and in school (Nesta, 2023).
- v. **Set Ethical Standards and Monitoring System:** To protect young learners, they must be clear ethical standards governing the use of AI in Social Studies Education. They should address privacy, safety, screen time limits and age- appropriate content. Regulatory agencies should be empowered to monitor AI tools and to enforce compliance.

References

- Adebanjo, R. & Salisu, H. (2023). Digital Transformation in Nigeria Education: The Role of Artificial Intelligence: *African Journal of ICT and Education*, 12 (1), 23-36.
- Anderson, S. & Makori, A. (2021). *Cultural Responsive Curriculum and A.I in Early Learning*.
- Eker, D. (2022). Parental and Educator Perceptions of Edtech in Nigeria Early Childhood Classrooms. *Journal of African Childhood Studies*, 8 (2), 44-59.
- Fital, R. (2025). *Inclusive Education with A.I. Supporting Special needs and Tackling Language*.

- Lawal, H. & Nojoko, P. N. (2025). *Assessment of Teachers Competence in Civic Education Curriculum Implementation in Senior Secondary Schools in Katsina State*. A Paper Presented at the 13th National Conference of Social Studies and Civic Educators Association of Nigeria held at Yusuf Maitama Sule Federal University of Education, Kano Between 4th – 8th & August, 2025.
- Luckin, R. Holmos, W. Griffiths, M. & Forcies, L.B/. (2016). *Intelligence Unleashed in an Argument for Ai in Education: Person Education*.
- Nesto (2023). *AI Early Eductaion Opportunity and Challenges*.
- Okonkwo, T. Adeyemi, B. (2023). Artificial Intelligence and Inclusive Early Childhood Education in Nigeria. *Journal of African Education Studies*, 7 (2), 112-124.
- Olam, C.C. (2019). *Twenty-First Century Expectations for Social Studies Education in Nigeria. The reading teacher: AREE Publishers and Research Editors Old Kaduna Road, Keffi-Nasarawa State, Cables, (2024). NGO Train north Central teachers an Integrating AI into Classroom Learning*.
- Guardian Nigeria (2023). *Incorporation AI into Curriculum ex-VC, Osofisan, Others WgeEG*.
- UNESCO, (2023). *Guidelines in AI in Education: Ethical and Practical Implications*.
- UNESCO (2023). *AI and Education: Guidance for Policy Makers: The United Nations Educational Scientific and Cultural Organization*.
- World Bank (2022). *Solar Powered Learning: Bridging the Energy and Education Divide in Sub-Sahara Africa*. Retrieved from <https://www.worldbank.org>
- Zawackj-Richter, O. Marin, V.I. Bond, M. & Gowermeur, F. (2022). *Systematic review of research on Artificial Intelligence in Education: Educational Research Review*; 34, 100387.

EVALUATION OF HIGHER EDUCATION INSTRUCTORS' PERCEPTION REGARDING THE INTEGRATION OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN TEACHING AND ASSESSMENT METHODS IN KANO STATE, NIGERIA

Tanimu Adam Ibrahim, PhD & Samira Abdullahi Bello, PhD

tanimuai@gmail.com

*Department of Curriculum and Instruction
Faculty of Education
Northwest University, Kano*

This research analyzed university instructors' perceptions toward the use of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in teaching and evaluation processes. The study is based on the UTAUT model and employs a descriptive survey approach. The study's participants included all academic staff from the 13 public and private universities in Kano State. To ensure adequate representation of each subgroup, participants were selected through a stratified random sampling method. This method involved first classifying the universities as either public or private, and then randomly sampling participants from each classification based on population proportions. A sample size of 370 instructors was collected as per the recommendation of the Research Advisor (2006) Guidelines. The data were analyzed through regression analysis and independent samples t-tests at a 0.05 significance level. The perceived benefits and ease of use were found to have a significant and positive impact on the intention to adopt AI, while perceived challenges had a strong negative effect. Facilitating conditions also had a significant but moderate positive impact. A distinct gap in readiness was found, suggesting instructors who had prior technology experience were more willing to adopt AI compared to their less experienced counterparts. The study concludes that successful AI integration in this context requires a multifaceted strategy addressing not only technological provision but also the development of institutional support systems, digital infrastructure, comprehensive training, and foundational digital literacy programs to bridge existing gaps and leverage AI's transformative potential effectively.

Keywords:
Artificial Intelligence (AI), Perceived ease of use, perceived usefulness, Technology Adoption, UTAUT, Instructors' Perception.

Introduction

Artificial Intelligence (AI) is rapidly transforming pedagogical nature and assessment methodologies across global higher education, contributing unique

opportunities for personalized learning, automated grading, enhanced feedback, and data-driven instructional decision-making (Zawacki-Richter et al., 2019; Chen et al.,